

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KINDO****FIRST NAME: SOULEYMANE****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is xx%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. **The institution of the EU, whose main objective is to support the creation, growth, and development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), is called:**

- European Investment Fund.¹**
- European Central Bank.
- European Investment Bank.
- European Court of Justice.

¹ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (European Union, 2021), 29.

2. **According to the European Union English style guide, every question that expects a separate answer should be followed by a question mark. Which sentence should be followed by a quotation mark?**

How will this affect EU trade.²

We should ask ourselves how this policy will affect EU trade.

Would you please sign and return the attached form.

Could you please sign and return the attached form.

3. **The European Union is regulated by a series of Treaties and various other agreements having similar status. Together, they constitute what is known as:**

Regulations.

Tertiary legislation.

Secondary legislation.

Primary legislation.³

4. **What treaty established the European Union in its actual name?**

The Euratom Treaty (Rome, 1957) established the European Atomic Energy Community.

The ECSC Treaty (Paris, 1951) established the European Coal and Steel Community.

² Ibid., 13.

³ Ibid., 72.

The EU Treaty (Maastricht, 1992).⁴

The EEC Treaty (Rome, 1957) established the European Economic Community.

5. **Which of the following best describes the meaning of primary sources?**

Sources like books, articles, papers, or reports based on oral sources intended for scholarly or professional audiences.

Sources like books, articles, papers, or reports based on original sources intended for scholarly or professional audiences.⁵

Sources like books and articles that synthesize non-original sources for general readers.

Sources like “original” materials that provide you with the “raw” data or evidence you will use to develop, test, and ultimately justify your hypothesis or claim.

6. **How can we recognize Applied Research?**

When the research addresses a conceptual problem, that does have practical consequences.⁶

When the research addresses a conceptual problem with no practical direct implications.

Consider your project’s significance: is it about understanding or doing?

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36–37.

⁶ Ibid., 29.

- When the research addresses a conceptual problem that does not have practical consequences.

7. **A What reason is not one of the four reasons to cite your sources:**

- To reassure readers about the inaccuracy of your facts.**⁷
- To give credit.
- To show readers the research tradition that informs your work.
- To help readers follow or extend your research.

8. **The process of writing a dissertation paper involves making four documents.**

Which document is not part of the four documents?

- The abstract.**⁸
- The dissertation concept paper.
- The dissertation prospectus.
- The dissertation manuscript.

9. **Factors that can lead to the successful completion of dissertation research.**

- Attention to detail.
- Good planning.
- Using an effective process of writing.

⁷ Ibid., 139.

⁸ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2–5.

All the above.⁹

10. When a writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information, taking someone else's words or ideas such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author or someone writing a paper for you, put your name on it, and give it to your professor is called:

Paraphrasing.

Academic writing.

Copying.

Plagiarism.¹⁰

⁹ Ibid., 13–14.

¹⁰ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/CA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.